

POLITICAL SYSTEM DURING THE REIGN OF BOQI MUHAMMADKHAN AND VALI MUHAMMADKHAN IN THE BUKHARA KHANATE**Beknazarov Javoxir Azimjon o'g'li**

Teacher of Samakand State Medical University,

E-mail: javohir_beknazarov@mail.ru.

ORCID ID: 0000-0006-5460-328X

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Buxoro xonligi hukmdori Boqi Muhammadxon va Vali Muhammadxonning tashqi siyosatdagi faoliyatlari, diplomatik aloqalari tahlil etilgan. Boqi Muhammadxonning Badakhshon tomon yo'l olish maqsadida qilgan harakatlari, Usmonli imperiyasi bilan elchilil aloqalari, Vali Muhammadning Shah Abbos bilan aloqalari tahlil etilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada Vali Muhammadxon va uning tarafdorlarining hukmdorlik uchun olib borgan kurashlari ham o'rganilgan. Ushbu davrda Buxoro Xonligi tashqi siyosati va diplomatiyasi ham tadqiq etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Buxoro Xonligi, Boqi Muhammadxon, Vali Muhammadxon, Diplomatiik aloqalar, Usmonli imperiyasi, Shah Abbos, Badakhshon, Xiva xonligi, Elchilar, O'zaro ittifoqlar.

Annotation: This article analyzes the foreign policy activities and diplomatic relations of Bukhara Khanate rulers Boqi Muhammad Khan and Vali Muhammad Khan. It examines Boqi Muhammad Khan's actions towards Badakhshan, his diplomatic relations with the Ottoman Empire, and Vali Muhammad Khan's relations with Shah Abbas. Additionally, the article explores the struggles of Vali Muhammad Khan and his supporters for sovereignty. The foreign policy and diplomacy of the Bukhara Khanate during this period are also studied.

Key words: Bukhara Khanate, Boqi Muhammad Khan, Vali Muhammad Khan, Diplomatic Relations, Ottoman Empire, Shah Abbas, Badakhshan, Khiva Khanate, Ambassadors, Mutual Alliances.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются внешнеполитическая деятельность и дипломатические отношения правителей Бухарского ханства, Боки Мухаммад хана и Вали Мухаммад хана. Рассматриваются действия Боки Мухаммад хана в сторону Бадахшана, его дипломатические отношения с Османской империей, а также отношения Вали Мухаммад хана с шахом Аббасом. Также в статье изучаются усилия Вали Мухаммад хана и его сторонников в борьбе за власть. Исследуется внешняя политика и дипломатия Бухарского ханства в этот период.

Ключевые слова: Бухарское ханство, Боки Мухаммад хан, Вали Мухаммад хан, дипломатические отношения, Османская империя, шах Аббас, Бадахшан, Хивинское ханство, послы, взаимные альянсы.

After Boqi Muhammad Khan took control of Balkh, he headed toward Badakhshan, which was ruled by Badi uz-Zaman. Upon hearing that Boqi Muhammad Khan was coming to conquer Badakhshan, Badi uz-Zaman sent an envoy to the Mughal ruler Akbar, requesting weapons and military aid. In response, Akbar sent 20 camels loaded with weapons and supplies to Badi uz-Zaman. However, the aid arrived too late. Subsequently, Akbar sent a letter to Boqi Muhammad Khan, promising that if he abandoned his plans to seize Badakhshan, Akbar would remain friendly. Nevertheless, Boqi Muhammad Khan and Vali Muhammad besieged and captured the city of Kunduz, where Badi uz-Zaman had settled, on March 25, 1603. Badi uz-Zaman and his close officials were executed. Angered by the execution of Badi uz-Zaman, Akbar sought to restore his reputation by launching a second campaign against Balkh and needed additional support. To achieve this, Boqi Muhammad Khan decided to request help from the Ottomans, who were traditional allies of the khanate. He sent an envoy to Sultan Mehmed III, reminding him of the historical diplomatic relations

between the Ottoman Empire and Bukhara. He mentioned the support Sultan Suleiman had shown to Baroq Khan and the diplomatic ties between Ottoman rulers and Abdullakhan II. Mehmed III, aware of the impending threat from the Safavids to the Ottoman Empire, warmly received the request. He ordered Abdul Boqi, the Shirvan governor, to supply Bukhara with weapons, sending 20 muskets, 3 cannons, and 200 arquebuses (a type of long gun) to help Boqi Muhammad Khan. (Orhonlu, C, 1970, 79-80-p) However, due to the Ottoman-Safavid War (1603-1612), the Ottomans could not provide further support, and Boqi Muhammad Khan did not use the weapons sent by Mehmed III. (A, Burton, 2019, 118-p) After the son of Keldi Muhammad seized Andijan, his Kazakh allies took control of a large area along the right bank of the Syr Darya, stretching from Tashkent in the south to Sighnaq in the north. Upon hearing this news, although suffering from an incurable illness, Boqi Muhammad Khan immediately set out from Samarkand to counter the invasion. His enemies, fearing his arrival, sent envoys to him in Khojand, offering to surrender. The Kazakhs and Keldi Muhammad's son recognized Boqi Muhammad Khan as their ruler and promised to cease oppressive actions, including collecting taxes and plundering. Boqi Muhammad Khan accepted their apology and promises sincerely, forgiving them and returning to Samarkand. (A, Burton, 2019, 122-p A, Vambery, 1873, 300-p)

Against Vali Muhammad, his nephews Nadr Muhammad and Imamqul Khan frequently revolted. (K. Salimiy, 2003, 270-272-p) Some officials also sided with these two nephews. Vali Muhammad Khan began eliminating their supporters and sought the help of Shah Abbas. In the spring of 1610, he began his plan, sending envoys to Khorasan to explain his intentions to establish friendly relations with Shah Abbas. Shah Abbas, still engaged in a struggle to regain territories lost to the Ottomans in the west, welcomed the opportunity to establish peace along his eastern borders, using the issue of Balkh as a pretext to interfere in Bukhara's affairs. He sent an envoy, Mirza Ali Bek, to Bukhara, and when he returned with Vali Muhammad's envoy, the Bukhara ambassador was warmly received. However, this diplomatic mission created a sense of discontent in Bukhara due to Shah Abbas's Shi'a affiliations.

In early 1611 (February-March), in a battle near Qarshi between Vali Muhammad and Imamqul Khan, Vali Muhammad retreated to Bukhara. However, he was unable to enter Bukhara and left for Chorjo'y with his wife Oyxonum and children. When Nadr Muhammad heard of the impending siege of Chorjo'y, he sent his son Rustam Sultan and his men to Herat. Vali Muhammad himself intended to go on a pilgrimage to Mecca and crossed into Iran. However, he was planning to restore his rule. Vali Muhammad and his supporters traveled through Marv, Mashhad, Bistam, Semnan, Khor and Keshan to Isfahan, where they were warmly welcomed by local governors, who presented lavish gifts. (A, Burton, 2019, 128-129-p)

The special gifts—horses adorned with jewels, furs, luxurious carpets, and fine fabrics—highlight the importance of diplomacy in consolidating political alliances.

Shah Abbas's offer to assist Vali Muhammad in regaining his throne, due to his ongoing war with the Ottomans, did not sit well with Vali Muhammad, who wanted to regain power sooner. Imamqul Khan, who had firmly established himself on the throne, was hesitant about accepting Shah Abbas's offer, fearing that it might lead to political instability. As a result, Vali Muhammad rejected the offer and decided to return to Bukhara with minimal help from Khorasan. He requested military assistance from Iran for his son Rustam Sultan, who was stationed in Herat.

In July 1611, a month after arriving in Isfahan, Vali Muhammad set out for Bukhara. Shah Abbas, who had left for Azerbaijan, provided him with horses, camels, tents, weapons, and funds for the journey. In the meantime, Nadr Muhammad sent congratulations to Jahangir, the Mughal ruler, on his ascension to the throne, explaining his previous delay in sending

congratulations due to the "Tashkent issue." He also hoped for future Mughal diplomatic missions.

In 1611, during the decisive battle between the uncles and nephews in Samarkand, the role of the Kazakh khans was significant. Initially, Abulay and his brother Buhung Sultan were expected to join Vali Muhammad's side. However, only Buhung Sultan arrived with 300 men, while Abulay Sultan, with 5,000 men, defected to Imamqul Khan's side. Buhung Sultan, who had initially joined Vali Muhammad's forces, defected to Imamqul Khan, creating disorder within Vali Muhammad's army.

In conclusion, The main events in Boqi Muhammad Khan's foreign policy and his just decisions deserve special attention. After Boqi Muhammad Khan captured Balkh, he engaged in a confrontation with Badi uz Zamon in order to seize Badakhshan. Moreover, he sought help from the Ottoman Empire to gain international support, which was crucial for the Bukhara Khanate. This article provides a detailed analysis of how the efforts to strengthen diplomatic relations and alliances yielded results, and how exchanges of gifts and the establishment of connections through ambassadors played a significant role. Additionally, the actions taken by Vali Muhammad Khan to reclaim his throne and his place in international politics are also discussed. During this period, Vali Muhammad successfully established diplomatic relations only with Iran. His limited political and economic influence was evident in his lack of engagement with Moscow and India. Additionally, his relations with the Nogai Khanate were restricted to supplying Russian slaves, showing Vali Muhammad's limited role in foreign politics and his greater focus on internal affairs.

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